

A REVIEW OF THE VALIDITY OF THE PURITY PROVISION OF SEC. 11 of ARTICLE II, OF RA 9165 “COMPREHENSIVE DANGEROUS DRUGS ACT”

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I. INTRODUCTION

Drug abuse remains a pervasive issue in the Philippines, with widespread use of both illicit and prescription drugs. According to the Dangerous Drugs Board (DDB) of the Philippines, an estimated 1.8 million Filipinos aged 10 to 69 years old are current drug users, representing approximately 2.3% of the population.¹

The former Philippine President Rodrigo R. Duterte undertook a controversial stance concerning Dangerous Drugs which is seemingly rooted in his experiences as Mayor of his home city – Davao². The War on Drugs, which is the moniker used by his administration to brand his series of incisive reforms within the law enforcement paradigms – not only created an international buzz, but more so, at the grassroots – precipitated the prevalence of drug busts which are marred by human rights issues³, and thus, drug cases in court⁴.

¹ Dangerous Drugs Board. (2020). 2019 Nationwide Survey on the Nature and Extent of Drug Abuse in the Philippines. <https://www.ddb.gov.ph/downloads/National%20Surveys/2019NS/Documents/2019NS%20Report.pdf>

² Kline, P. (2020, October 28). Rodrigo Duterte: The rise of Philippines' death squad mayor. Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2015/07/17/rodrigo-duterte-rise-philippines-death-squad-mayor>

³ Luna, F. (2022, November 18). Rights watchdog hits PNP for “undercounting” Drug War killings under Marcos. Philstar.com. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2022/11/18/2224747/rights-watchdog-hits-pnp-undercounting-drug-war-killings-under-marcos>

⁴ Caliwan, C. L. (2022, September 2). PDEA working hard to improve conviction rate of drug cases | Philippine News Agency. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1183319>

One effect of this war on drugs is the increase in the opportunity of the courts and legal professionals to review certain aspects of the law on these Dangerous Drugs - R.A. 9165 or the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002.

One such opportunity transpired in the Regional Trial Court of Dipolog City, 9th Judicial Region Br. 9, when the curious case of Alfred St. George raised the question of the fairness of the purity provision of Sec. 11 of Art. II of R.A. 9165.

The Drug Case of Alfred St. George⁵

Alfred St. George, a Canadian Citizen, who visited the Philippines, particularly, Dipolog City, Zamboanga del Norte, to be with his Filipina lover, whom he met online, due to a confluence of circumstances, became a legal aid client of IBP Zamboanga del Norte Chapter, having sought the latter's assistance when he was jailed for alleged violations of Article II, Sections 5, 11, and 12 of RA 9165 – otherwise known as the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002.⁶

On September 2, 2018, a couple of months after arriving in Dipolog City, Zamboanga del Norte, St. George decided to rent an apartment unit in one of the predominantly residential barangays in the area, Brgy. Dicayas, Dipolog City.

⁵ Crim. Cases No. 22686/22687/22694. Regional Trial Court 9th Judicial Region Branch 9, Dipolog City.

⁶ Information. Records. See Note 5

However, on September 7, 2018, only five days after he moved into his apartment, St. George was arrested by the officers of the Drug Enforcement Unit in Dipolog City for allegedly selling and possessing dangerous drugs and drug paraphernalia during a buy-bust operation in violation of R.A. 9165 or the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002.

St. George claimed that the buy-bust operation was a sham.

According to St. George, in the afternoon of September 7, 2018, he was sleeping inside one of the rooms of his two-bedroom apartment, when he heard a knock at his door. Upon opening his door, he was surprised to find armed men in civilian clothes. The armed men, who he later learned were members of the Dipolog City Drug Enforcement Unit, restrained, immobilized, and handcuffed him. His entire apartment was searched without a warrant, and the contents of his refrigerator, which included cookies and Marijuana leaves, were confiscated. After the search, the police officers started preparing for the conduct of an inventory of seized items. Hours after his illegal arrest, the instrumental witnesses, i.e., the barangay captain of Dicayas, Dipolog City, and a representative from the Department of Justice, arrived to witness the inventory.

After the conduct of the inventory of the seized items, St. George was instructed to sign the Inventory Sheet, but he refused. He was brought to the police station for investigation, and subsequently to the crime laboratory for drug examination. From the

time of his arrest up to his detention, St. George was not represented by a lawyer.

St. George was detained at the Dipolog City Jail without recommended bail as Sec. 5 Article II of RA 9165 is a non-bailable offense. As for the charge of possession of prohibited drugs under Sec. 11 Art. II of RA 9165, which was relative to the confiscated cookies allegedly laced with Marijuana, the mass of 460g, being more than 300g and less than 500g, carried with it a penalty of twenty years and one day to life imprisonment.

The amounts of the seized materials disqualified St. George from availing of the Plea-Bargaining Framework of the Court for Drug cases, thus he was forced to proceed with trial.

In November 2018, two months after St. George was arrested and detained, the IBP Zamboanga del Norte Chapter conducted a jail visitation with free legal consultation at the Dipolog City Jail. During the jail visitation, St. George expressed that he did not get to have a chance to talk to a private lawyer and that he wanted to avail of the free legal services of the Chapter's Legal Aid Office. On November 18, 2018, the IBP Zamboanga del Norte Chapter accepted St. George's application for free legal representation.

Ultimately, St. George was arraigned in Branch 9 of the Regional Trial Court of Dipolog City. He was charged for violating Sections 5, 11, and 12 of R.A. 9165. Assisted by the legal aid lawyers of IBP Zamboanga del Norte Chapter, St. George entered a plea of not guilty.

The Canadian Embassy contacted the Legal Aid Office of IBP Zamboanga del Norte and monitored the development of the case.

From 2019 to 2020, St. George's case was heard. The Prosecution presented five witnesses: (1) the Chemist, (2) the Evidence Custodian, (3) the Crime Laboratory's Officer of the Day (4) the Arresting Officer, and the (5) Poseur Buyer.

After the Prosecution rested their case, St. George, through his lawyer, filed a Motion for Leave to File a Demurrer to Evidence, and subsequently his Demurrer to Evidence arguing in essence that the Prosecution failed to prove that the integrity and evidentiary value of the dangerous drugs was preserved.

On September 24, 2020, the trial court denied St. George's Demurrer to Evidence. On October 6, 2020, St. George's lawyer filed a Motion for Reconsideration. The trial court granted the Motion for Reconsideration and consequently acquitted St. George of all the criminal charges.

St. George was acquitted, finally and he has, since his acquittal returned to his home country, Canada.

Notwithstanding the favorable resolution of this case for the accused St. George, an interesting legal question was raised particularly when Police Lieutenant Colonel Melvin Ledesma Manuel – a lawyer and licensed chemist – was made to testify as the PNP Chemist who conducted the testing.

For purposes of this witness, herein representation was engaged by the IBP Legal Aid Center of IBP Zamboanga del Norte, being a volunteer lawyer of the latter, for having special expertise as a Licensed Chemist, much like the witness, with the special purpose of ascertaining the legal and factual background of the testing done on the alleged Marijuana Laced Cookies.

At this point, it would be instructive to inspect the very law on which the charges are anchored.

“Section 11. *Possession of Dangerous Drugs.* - The penalty of life imprisonment to death and a fine ranging from Five hundred thousand pesos (P500,000.00) to Ten million pesos (P10,000,000.00) shall be imposed upon any person, who, unless authorized by law, shall possess any dangerous drug in the following quantities, **regardless of the degree of purity thereof:**

xxx

(7) 500 grams or more of marijuana; and

xxx

(2) Imprisonment of twenty (20) years and one (1) day to life imprisonment and a fine ranging from Four hundred thousand pesos (P400,000.00) to Five hundred thousand pesos (P500,000.00), if the quantities of dangerous drugs are five (5) grams or more but less than ten (10) grams

of opium, morphine, heroin, cocaine or cocaine hydrochloride, marijuana resin or marijuana resin oil, methamphetamine hydrochloride or "shabu", or other dangerous drugs such as, but not limited to, MDMA or "ecstasy", PMA, TMA, LSD, GHB, and those similarly designed or newly introduced drugs and their derivatives, without having any therapeutic value or if the quantity possessed is far beyond therapeutic requirements; **or three hundred (300) grams or more but less than five (hundred) 500) grams of marijuana**; and

(3) Imprisonment of twelve (12) years and one (1) day to twenty (20) years and a fine ranging from Three hundred thousand pesos (P300,000.00) to Four hundred thousand pesos (P400,000.00), if the quantities of dangerous drugs are less than five (5) grams of opium, morphine, heroin, cocaine or cocaine hydrochloride, marijuana resin or marijuana resin oil, methamphetamine hydrochloride or "shabu", or other dangerous drugs such as, but not limited to, MDMA or "ecstasy", PMA, TMA, LSD, GHB, and those similarly designed or newly introduced drugs and their derivatives, without having any therapeutic value or if the quantity possessed is far beyond therapeutic requirements; **or less than three hundred (300) grams of marijuana.**

xxX.⁷"

⁷ Emphasis Supplied

Emphasized therein is the clause that is at the very core of the St. George Case and this article, that the measurements of quantities are "REGARDLESS OF THE DEGREE OF PURITY THEREOF..."

This was the very reason why the Chemist had to be cross-examined extensively as an expert, because how the measurement of the existence of marijuana was done was material to the case at bar. St. George would suffer less penalty if the amount of marijuana established was less as well – this can be gleaned from. Sec. 11 itself where three separate ranges of penalty are presented depending on the amount of the confiscated marijuana.

Therefore, the law admits that it is but appropriate to give lesser penalties if the amount of the seized prohibited drugs is also lesser, this reinforces our initial humble submission that the notion that "degree of purity", is rendered immaterial by reason of the word "regardless", which goes directly against the standard imposed by the law itself – since lesser drugs should result in lesser penalties.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Is the provision in Sec. 11 of Article II of R.A. 9165, particularly the weight qualification that states that it is REGARDLESS OF DEGREE OF PURITY valid?

If the degree of purity is disregarded, in the same way, that it was disregarded in the St. George Case, then a bag of unadulterated cookies which was mixed up with some cookies that had marijuana in them, thus contaminating the whole bag, would likewise test positive

for marijuana, thus the entire bulk, including those cookies not laced with marijuana would be weighed and this total mass will be considered to be the mass of marijuana.

This is not even at all *just* an issue of penalty. In fact, it goes deeper into our judicial system since the weight of the drug specimen is also indicative of the viability of Plea Bargaining and consequently Applying for Probation.

It should be noted that under the prevailing plea-bargaining framework⁸ of the Supreme Court for the three ranges of punishment for the possession of marijuana under Sec. 11 of Art. II of RA 9165 has specified allowable plea-bargain set-ups as follows:

For Possession of a weighed mass of Marijuana that is more than 500g punished under par. 1 of Sec. 11, no plea bargain is allowed. On the other hand, Possession of a weighed mass of Marijuana that is not more than 500g but not less than 300g under par. 2 of Sec. 11, the acceptable plea-bargain is to par. 3 of Sec. 11, the penalty, instead of a penalty of 20 years to life imprisonment, as is prescribed under par. 2 of Sec. 11, of which is 12 years and 1 day to twenty years. Lastly, still under the framework mentioned herein, if the weighed mass of the marijuana is less than 300g, then the acceptable plea-bargain shall be to Sec. 12 of the same act, which has the penalty of, instead of a penalty of 12 years and one day to 20 years, as is prescribed under par. 3 of Sec. 11, 6 months and 1 day to 4 years under Sec. 12.⁹

⁸ OCA Circular No. 90-2018

⁹ See Note 8

A cursory look at this framework would reveal the simple conclusion that if the weighed amount of the Marijuana were less than 300g, then a Plea Bargain would necessarily allow for the Application for Probation since the penalty in such a case is non-disqualificatory for probation¹⁰ under our prevailing laws.

With the legal frameworks that take into consideration the amount of the seized drugs under RA 9165, and the Plea-Bargaining Framework for Drug Cases of the Supreme Court which considers the amount as charged as determinative of the allowable plea-bargain – it is obvious that our legal system affirms that in this case that the WEIGHT OF THE PROHIBITED DRUGS IS MATERIAL.

If so, then there should be no question that the manner of ascertaining the mass of the seized marijuana should not be dismissive of the concept of purity.

This idea that the range of penalties should consider the amount of the marijuana seized is part of a greater more well-entrenched legal principle of Commensurability of penalties as a Juridical Condition.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE, LAWS, AND JURISPRUDENCE

¹⁰ Sec. 9 of PD 968 as amended by RA 10707

Juridical Conditions of Penalties; Commensurability

It is well established in our jurisdiction that a Penalty, in its most basic form, is any sort of burden or suffering meted by the State by reason of a person's transgression of law.

However, such burden or suffering cannot just be made without any form of standard. In fact, under the Classical School which is the basis of our Revised Penal Code, according to Legal Luminaries and Bastions of Philippine Criminal Law, Former Chief Justice Diosdado Peralta¹¹ and Ret. CA Justice Luis B. Reyes¹² have opined in their respective books that penalties are subject to the following juridical conditions:

1. Must be productive of suffering – limited by the integrity of human personality.
2. Must be proportionate to the crime.
3. Must be personal – imposed only upon the criminal.
4. Must be legal – according to a judgment of fact and law.
5. Must be equal – applies to everyone regardless of the circumstance; and
6. Must be correctional – to rehabilitate the offender.

¹¹ Peralta, D. (2021). Title Three: Penalties, Chapter One: Penalties in General. In *Essentials in Criminal Law Book I*, Rex Bookstore.

¹² Reyes, L. B. (2021). Title Three: Penalties, Chapter One: Penalties in General. In *The Revised Penal Code (20th ed.)*, Rex Bookstore.

For purposes of this study, it is the condition of commensurability or proportionality of the penalty to the crime that finds relevance.

Truly undeniable is the fact that in the realm of jurisprudence, the concept of commensurability holds significant weight, particularly concerning the imposition of penalties in legal systems not just in the Philippines, but across various jurisdictions. It requires reiteration that commensurability refers to the principle that penalties must be proportionate to the gravity of the offense committed. This principle ensures fairness, equity, and justice in the administration of law. In the Philippine legal system, commensurability serves as a guiding principle in determining appropriate penalties for various offenses.

In Philippine law, commensurability is deeply rooted in the constitutional principle of due process. Article III, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution guarantees that "No person shall be deprived of life, liberty, or property without due process of law."¹³ This provision encompasses the notion that any penalty imposed must be commensurate with the offense committed, ensuring that individuals are not subjected to arbitrary or excessive punishments. It is elementary that substantive due process, in its most basic iteration "requires the intrinsic validity of the law in interfering with the rights of the person to his life, liberty, or property."¹⁴

¹³ Sec. 1 Article III. 1987 Philippine Constitution

¹⁴ Secretary of Justice v. Lantion (G.R. No. 139465 , January 18, 2000).

Moreover, the Revised Penal Code (RPC)¹⁵ of the Philippines, enacted in 1930, provides the statutory framework for defining criminal offenses and prescribing penalties. Article 25 of the RPC emphasizes the principle of commensurability by stating that "penalties which are prescribed by law shall be imposed upon any person who shall commit a felony." This provision underscores the importance of aligning penalties with the gravity of the offense to maintain the balance between justice and proportionality.

Furthermore, the Philippine legal system acknowledges the significance of international human rights standards in ensuring commensurability in penalties. The Philippines is a signatory to various international treaties and conventions, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR¹⁶) and the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CAT)¹⁷. At their very core, these international documents have the intent to emphasize that all member states must uphold the principle of proportionality in imposing penalties and prevent the use of excessive or disproportionate punishment.

¹⁵ ACT No. 3815 (December 8, 1930). Philippines.

¹⁶ UN General Assembly, *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 999, p. 171, 16 December 1966, <https://www.refworld.org/legal/agreements/unga/1966/en/17703>

¹⁷ UN General Assembly, *Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment*, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 1465, p. 85, 10 December 1984, <https://www.refworld.org/legal/agreements/unga/1984/en/13941>

In the book "Sentencing and Human Rights: The Limits on Punishment"¹⁸, particularly Chapter 3 thereof entitled Proportionality, the author Prof. Sarah J. Summers of the University of Zurich in citing relevant legal publications posited that proportionality acts as a constraint on the state's power to punish individuals by restricting the extent to which it is entitled to interfere with an individual's human rights and fundamental freedoms.

Hence, a state, such as the Philippines, that purports to be democratic, must adhere to the basic tenet of proportionality of penalty.

In an Estafa Case tried before the Supreme Court, the majority ruling was for the application of the provisions of the Indeterminate Sentence Law as it was during that time. However, in a Dissenting Opinion Justice Presbitero Velasco submitted "*that [the] principle of proportionality between the offense committed and the penalty imposed finds application in determining the penalty for the crime of estafa. The penalty for estafa must always be commensurate with the amount defrauded. If the concept of proportionality between the offense committed and the sanction imposed is not strictly adhered to, then unfairness and injustice will inevitably result.*"¹⁹

The dissenting opinion underscores the need to look at penalty through the lens of fairness and justice – putting a premium on the proportionality of the penalty to the act or omission it is implemented to address.

¹⁸ Summers, Sarah J, 'Proportionality', *Sentencing and Human Rights: The Limits on Punishment* (Oxford, 2022; online edn, Oxford Academic, 15 Dec. 2022),

¹⁹ People v. Temporada (G.R. No. 173473) Dissenting Opinion. Justice Presbitero Velasco

In the case of *Corpuz v. People*²⁰, Dean Jose Manuel I. Diokno, an amicus curiae of the Supreme Court cited the Landmark US Case of *Solem v. Helm*²¹ and stated that “the United States Federal Supreme Court has expanded the application of a similar Constitutional provision prohibiting cruel and unusual punishment, to the duration of the penalty, and not just its form. The court therein ruled that three things must be done to decide whether a sentence is proportional to a specific crime, viz.; (1) Compare the nature and gravity of the offense and the harshness of the penalty; (2) Compare the sentences imposed on other criminals in the same jurisdiction, i.e., whether more serious crimes are subject to the same penalty or to less serious penalties; and (3) Compare the sentences imposed for commission of the same crime in other jurisdictions.”

The cruelty of a punishment is not merely a matter of form but likewise may be expressed in a disproportionate length thereof.

However, it would be unethical not to cite at this point not to cite another US Case where no less than Justice Antonin Scalia made a clarification on the matter of disproportionality - *Harmelin v. Michigan*²².

In sum, the US Federal Supreme Court posited that “a criminal sentence is generally constitutional if a state has a reasonable basis for believing that the sentence will further any of the four main purposes of punishment: deterrence, retribution, rehabilitation, or

²⁰ *Corpuz v. People*. (G.R. No. 180016, April 29, 2014)

²¹ *Solem v. Helm*, 463 U.S. 277 (1983)

²² See Note 23

incapacitation. The Eighth Amendment does not require strict proportionality between crime and sentence, forbidding only a sentence that is grossly disproportionate to the crime.”²³

Is it grossly disproportional then for an accused to suffer life imprisonment, for a miniscule amount of the prohibited drug, which weighs more because of the inclusion of other materials in the weighing of the drug? This question is answered in the discussions of this paper.

III – METHODOLOGY

This article aims to analyze Sec. 11 of Article II, of the Comprehensive Drugs Act of 2002 (R.A. 9165), particularly the implications of the “regardless of purity” qualification in the measurement of the prohibited drugs as against the existing procedures within the context of Marijuana Testing as a prohibited drug in the Philippines and according to prevailing Philippine National Police Manuals and Issuances and analyze their relevance, effectiveness, and applicability to the St. George Case. By employing a qualitative approach, the study seeks to understand the broader context of existing circumstances of the law’s deliberations while examining how this law is implemented and adapted in real-world settings. The methodology outlined below is the structured framework employed in the conduct of the research, encompassing data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

²³ US Supreme Court, J. (Ed.). (n.d.). *Harmelin v. Michigan*, 501 U.S. 957 (1991). Justia Law. <https://supreme.justia.com/cases/federal/us/501/957/#annotation>

1. Research Design:

The research done for the article involved a qualitative exploration and analysis of existing procedures through document analysis and observations, as well as a thematic analysis in the context of case records and Congressional Records.

2. Qualitative Phase:

Document analysis: Relevant documents, such as policy manuals, procedural guidelines, and organizational reports, were reviewed to gain insights into the structure, content, and objectives of existing procedures in Dangerous Drugs Testing. Court records of Crim Cases Nos. 22686/22687/22694²⁴ are analyzed as to the facts and details of the test-case of *People v. St. George*. Furthermore, Congressional Records²⁵, particularly on the 2nd hearing on the Senate Bill No. 1858 that would later be enacted as R.A. 9165 is also analyzed to provide contextualization which is later used in the thematic analysis of the provision of law being reviewed – Sec. 11, Rule 2, of R.A 9165.

Thematic analysis: Court transcripts of the *St. George* Case, Congressional Records, and document excerpts were analyzed thematically to identify key themes, patterns, and issues related to existing procedures.

²⁴ See note 6

²⁵ Record of the Senate. First Regular Session September 27 – December 22, 2001. Volume II. No. 33. (October 22, 2001)

Triangulation: Findings from interviews, document analysis, and observations were triangulated to enhance the validity and reliability of results and provide a comprehensive understanding of existing procedures.

3. Ethical Considerations:

Use of the Case of Alfred St. George: The use and dissection of the People v. Alfred St. George case was done without redaction of names of persons involved in the case as the accused therein and all participants are no longer minors and do not enjoy confidentiality of the case as it forms part of public records.

Use of Congressional Records: Congressional Records specifically the transcript of the deliberations of R.A. 9165 prior to its enactment are part of public records – personalities therein, particularly the Senators quoted herein operated in their capacity as public officials during a session that forms part of public records.

Use of Artificial Intelligence: Artificial Intelligence was employed solely as a writing tool such as in the paraphrasing of properly cited content, proofreading and copy-editing, formatting of foot-note citations, and general text constructions based on the author's textual inputs.

Conclusion:

This research methodology provides a systematic approach for investigating existing procedures and their application to a specific case study. By employing a qualitative approach, the study aims to generate comprehensive insights that can inform decision-making, policy development, and procedural improvements within the context of legislation.

IV – ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Commensurability of the Penalty in the St. George Case

The concept of commensurability was sought to be proved as fact in the St. George Case when a line of questioning was undertaken by counsel during the trial specifically emphasizing this exact legal principle:

Q. ([Atty. Cielo] So, could you tell this Court with the two examinations that you performed, what is the detection limit? The least detection limits.

A: [PLC Manuel] Sir, if you're talking of the TLC, the detection limit is parts per billion. I can still remember if you're talking of methamphetamine, the detection limit of your TLC is 2 parts per billion. For this case it's around 10 or 20 ppb.

Q: Mr. Witness, since not everyone in this Court is well-versed as to what does parts per billion means, can you tell this Court if that amount is very, very small or very, very large?

A: That amount is very, very small.

Q: Because that would mean that for every one part, there's a billion other parts of the solution. Correct?

A: Yes, Sir.

Q: That means that your testing, for example, if I have a single powder or a drop of this marijuana extract in a gallon of water, your test will test positive. Is that correct?

A: If the drop would be equal to the detection limit, it would give you a positive result but if the concentration falls below the detection limit of the instrument, it will give you a negative result.²⁶

Here lies the absurdity – a drop of marijuana extract which would weigh less than a gram, could weigh a staggering 1000 grams simply because it met a substance in which it was mixed.

During the trial, this was further emphasized with an analysis of detection limits and how that relates to the above illustration.

Q: Mr. Witness, these cookies, as a chemist, how would you describe the type of mixture the cookies have relative to the alleged marijuana?

A: Composition. I cannot estimate the proportion of the flour, sugar, and the butter in relation to the grounded marijuana seeds and leaves, Sir.

²⁶ Page 12. Transcript of Stenographic Notes (October 29, 2019). Records. Supra 5

Q: Just to clarify. In your qualitative testing, you would not be able to know that also.

A: Yes.

Q: So, could you tell this Court with the two examinations that you performed, what is the detection limit? The least detection limits.

A: Sir, if you're talking of the TLC, the detection limit is parts per billion. I can still remember if you're talking of methamphetamine, the detection limit of your TLC is 2 parts per billion. For this case it's around 10 or 20 ppb.

Q: Mr. Witness, since not everyone in this Court is well-versed as to what does parts per billion means, can you tell this Court if that amount is very, very small or very, very large?

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A: Yes, Sir.

Q: That means that your testing, for example, if I have a single powder or a drop of this marijuana extract in a gallon of water, your test will test positive. Is that correct?

A: If the drop would be equal to the detection limit, it would give you a positive result but if the concentration falls below the detection limit of the instrument, it will give you a negative result.

Q: So, it is possible also that for example, in a situation such as in the case at bar, these are food products, if the food product is, say for example, adulterated by mistake or accident by few powders of marijuana, once tested, it would test positive. Would that be correct?

A: There's a probability. If the adulterant exceeds the detection limit, it will give you a positive result. So, contaminants. It will be contaminated.

Q: So, say for example, these cookies, if there's a mixture now of the cookies with regards to ordinary cookies and cookies that are laced by marijuana, would the other cookies when they come in close contact, is it possible that they would also yield a positive result?

A: There is a possibility that the unlaced cookies will now be contaminated by the cookies that have marijuana, Sir.

Q: And would it yield a positive result in your testing?

A: It might give a positive result if it goes beyond the detection limit of the examination, Sir. ²⁷

This bolsters the idea that a disregard of the actual amount of the marijuana present would violate the concept of Commensurability, if it is made the basis for penalty which is absolutely the case in Sec. 11, Art. II, RA 9165 – the very law we are reviewing, because it is possible that a positive test would be yielded by a sample that is only 0.000002% which is essentially 20 ppb (parts per billion).

²⁷ Page 12 – 13. Transcript of Stenographic Notes (October 29, 2019). Records. Supra 5

SENATE DELIBERATIONS ON THE PURITY ISSUE

The question on inclusions in the weighing of the drug was discussed during the deliberations of R.A. 9165 before the Philippine Senate where the issue of Purity as a disregarded factor in the determination of extent of liability was raised by Senator Rodolfo Biazon.

"Senator Biazon. *Thank you, Mr. President.*

Here is my second question, Mr. President. Section 9 of the bill provides the quantities of dangerous drugs punishable by life imprisonment to death. In determining the quantities, the bill uses the phrase "regardless of the degree of purity or quality." Does this phrase, in effect, classify the additives as also dangerous drugs?

Senator Barbers. *Is the gentleman referring to the additives in what prohibited drugs?*

Senator Biazon. *Section 9, Mr. President of the bill.*

Senator Barbers. *Yes, Mr. President. I would say, it includes the additives. Because the phrase "regardless of the degree of purity or quality" is prominently underscored. So whether it is an A1 or an A2 or an A3 as long as it is a dangerous drug, it falls within the violation.*

Senator Blazon. Which means, Mr. President, what is being weighed is not only the pure dangerous drugs if separated from the combination but including the additives especially on shabu

Senator Barbers. That is correct, Mr. President.

Senator Biazon. So, is this really the intent, Mr. President?

Senator Barbers. Mr. President, we are doing this because in the manufacture of shabu, it is necessary to use additives. To purify the finished product of shabu, additives or some chemicals are to be used in order to come up with a quality, in order to come up with an A1 purity.

Senator Biazon. Mr. President, for example, one individual is caught in possession of pure shabu in one pocket and additives in the other pocket, but the pure shabu is not of the weight that is so defined, how do we treat this?

Senator Barbers. Mr. President, if the arrest is made on a person with only additives in his possession, that would not fall under this provision. But if the person is arrested with, let us say, one gram of shabu, mixed with additives, it falls within the provision.

Senator Biazon. Therefore, if I have in my possession, in my left pocket an amount of shabu the weight of which would make me as vulnerable to life imprisonment, but is less... Meaning, if I have an amount of pure shabu in my left pocket, less than the required amount that would merit life imprisonment or death, and in my right pocket, I have additives which if combined with

the shabu, total a weight that would merit a death penalty, how do we treat this?

Senator Barbers. *What is being contemplated, Mr. President, is that the additives must be in the shabu itself In other words, the additives must not be separated from the shabu. And now if the additives are considered as precursors or essential chemicals, these fall under the violation, Mr. President.*

Senator Biazon. *Yes, even if these are separately carried?*

Senator Barbers. *That is correct, Mr. President.*

Senator Biazon. *I would like to thank the sponsor, Mr. President.*²⁸

Senator Biazon's illustration is precisely what the court was confronted with in the St. George Case. It would appear that even if one has less than the amount stated in the law that would warrant the imposition of life imprisonment, because of the phrasing of the law in stating that the weight is "regardless of purity", the accused is indeed "vulnerable to life imprisonment", as how Senator Biazon put it.

However, what is most revealing is not the incisive questioning of Senator Biazon, but the responses of the sponsor of the Senate Bill himself, Senator Robert Barbers when he seemingly conflates the scientific concepts of a mixture and a compound.

THE CHEMISTRY OF ADDITIVES

²⁸ Page 66. Supra Note 25

What is Senator Barbers referring to when he stated that what is contemplated in the purity non-qualification is that the additive “must be in the shabu itself”?

When a separate substance is “in” another, it could mean many things. It could be that it is compounded into the substance itself, or it might be a mixture.

Elementary concepts in Chemistry would tell us that “a **mixture** is a **combination**²⁹ of two or more substances in any proportion. This is different from a compound, which consists of substances in fixed proportions. The substances in a mixture also do not combine chemically to form a new substance, as they do in a compound. Instead, they just intermingle and keep their original properties.”³⁰

In all fairness, Senator Barbers might just well be referring to compounds which “can generally be classified into two broad groups: molecular compounds and ionic compounds. Molecular compounds involve atoms joined by covalent bonds and can be represented by a variety of formulas. Ionic compounds are composed of ions joined by ionic bonding, and their formulas are generally written using oxidation states. Molecular compounds are composed of atoms that are held together by covalent bonds. These bonds are formed when electrons are shared between two atoms. The concept of chemical formulas was

²⁹ Emphasis Supplied

³⁰ Libretexts, C.-12 F. (Ed.). (2022, September 20). 2.7: Mixture. Chemistry LibreTexts. [https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Introductory_Chemistry/Introductory_Chemistry_\(CK-12\)/02%3A_Matter_and_Change/2.07%3A_Mixture](https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Introductory_Chemistry/Introductory_Chemistry_(CK-12)/02%3A_Matter_and_Change/2.07%3A_Mixture)

created to describe many characteristics of molecular compounds in a simple manner. A normal chemical formula encompasses factors such as which elements are in the molecule and how many atoms of each element there are. The number of atoms of each element is denoted by a subscript, a small number that is written to the left of the element."³¹

In sum, the difference therefore is whether or not there is a chemical reaction that creates either ionic or molecular bonds, or is there merely a physical mixing, that creates intermolecular bonding that creates a mixture – separable by physical means, while the former undergoes a chemical reaction and thus requires a chemical reaction in its separation.

So, what was being referred to in their deliberation? The key here is the term purity.

Purity in a chemical sense will only refer to such a situation when one substance mingles with another in a state of physical combination. So that the degree or amount of one substance to the other is the ratio that is referred to as its Purity that is expressed in orders of CONCENTRATION such as in percentile, per billion, per million, molarity, molality, and even normality. ³²

³¹ Libretexts. (2023, June 30). Chemical Compounds. Chemistry LibreTexts. [https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Inorganic_Chemistry/Supplemental_Modules_and_Websites_\(Inorganic_Chemistry\)/Chemical_Compounds/Chemical_Compounds](https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Inorganic_Chemistry/Supplemental_Modules_and_Websites_(Inorganic_Chemistry)/Chemical_Compounds/Chemical_Compounds)

³² Study Rocket. (2019, July 8). Purity and mixtures – GCSE chemistry (Combined science) ocr revision. <https://studyrocket.co.uk/revision/gcse-chemistry-combined-science-ocr/elements-compounds-and-mixtures/purity-and-mixtures>

There is therefore no question of purity, when a substance is added to another so that they form a new chemical compound – this is the case of precursor chemicals as defined under R.A. 9165. When precursor chemicals are added to each other, they form chemical bonds that create a new chemical.

This is precisely what happens in the case of SHABU or Methamphetamine Hydrochloride where precursor chemicals such as Benzaldehyde and Nitro-Ethane are combined to form 1-Phenyl-2-Nitropropene, which is further reacted in catalyst to P-2-P, a major precursor for amphetamine products in the same manner as ephedrine and pseudoephedrine are used to manufacture methamphetamine.³³

When this product is produced, and **if only this product exists in a sample**, it is considered a pure substance because no other chemical is present therein.

This point here does beg the question – could it be that Senator Barbers, when referring to the concept of Purity is referring to an instance when these dangerous drugs were undergoing organic synthesis, actually was referring to the scientific fact that no one can chemically produce a 100% pure product?

When chemicals are produced, the various chemical stages and processes make it impossible that the end product is 100% pure as

³³ Precursors and chemicals frequently used in the illicit ... International Narcotics Control Board. (n.d.). https://www.incb.org/documents/PRECURSORS/TECHNICAL_REPORTS/2020/E/Report_B_reakdown/08_Extent_of_licit_trade_and_latest_trends_in_trafficking_in_precursors.pdf

impurities are produced³⁴ by way of isomeric variance³⁵, inclusions of catalysts, or even unreacted precursor chemicals – all of this is in fact the driving force behind a chemical industry of purification and a science all to itself that seeks to ensure there is close to 100% of a product in a given sample, most particularly in the field of medicine.³⁶

In this case, the intent of the producer, and possessor and the seller, because they cannot make the substance 100% pure, is really to possess that number of dangerous drugs, regardless of purity.

However, the provision does not admit the aforementioned logical interpretation. The law includes the fact that purity likewise looks at an instance where additives can be mixed to produce desired results.

For economic reasons, for example, a sample of pure methamphetamine may be mixed with subliming solids such as ammonia which happened in Cebu City in 2011 when accused Alias Tortor commented in the discovery of ammonium nitrate in the seized shabu as having been added to increase the weight of the shabu upon selling it.³⁷

³⁴ StudySmarter GbmH. (n.d.). Purification. StudySmarter UK.
<https://www.studysmarter.co.uk/explanations/chemistry/organic-chemistry/purification/>

³⁵ Libretexts. (2023a, April 12). 23.3: Isomers of organic compounds. Chemistry LibreTexts.
[https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/General_Chemistry/Book%3A_General_Chemistry%3A_Principles_Patterns_and_Applications_\(Averill\)/23%3A_Organic_Compounds/23.03%3A_Isomers_of_Organic_Compounds](https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/General_Chemistry/Book%3A_General_Chemistry%3A_Principles_Patterns_and_Applications_(Averill)/23%3A_Organic_Compounds/23.03%3A_Isomers_of_Organic_Compounds)

³⁶ Organic Process Research & Development 2012 16 (12), 1877-1877
DOI: 10.1021/op300317g

³⁷ Sorote, R. C. J. (n.d.). Police seize shabu mixed with ammonia. Philstar.com.
<https://www.philstar.com/cebu-news/2011/08/31/721959/police-seize-shabu-mixed-ammonia>

As for Marijuana, or other Cannabis products, although being plant-based materials, these are nonetheless added in mixtures not to increase their weight, but to add to the experience of taking it certain factors.

In the case of St. George, the allegation was that Marijuana was baked into cookies so as to quell the hunger experience when taking Marijuana as a narcotic.

True enough, in the study by Ifkithar, et al. (2021) it was found that Cannabis's alimentary usage accounts for 7.29% of all uses in the global CANNUSE database, with 58.72% of them corresponding to traditional meals and 41.28% to traditional beverages. Varieties of such usage of Cannabis range from beverages to desserts such as chocolates and baked goods, to adding Cannabis in pickles, oils, and even in preparations of gummies.³⁸

In all these usages, the same study found the amount of cannabis found varies drastically. Cookies in particular have been shown to "have different concentrations of raw and roasted hemp flour were added instead of wheat flour. The incorporation of hemp flour (raw or roasted) in cookies resulted in enhanced total phenolic content, antioxidant activity, ash, protein, and fat contents, with the highest parameters recorded at a 20% concentration. Hemp flour reduced the toughness of the cookies, resulting in softer cookies.

³⁸ Iftikhar, A., Zafar, U., Ahmed, W., Shabbir, M. A., Sameen, A., Sahar, A., Bhat, Z. F., Kowalczewski, P. Ł., Jarzębski, M., & Aadil, R. M. (2021). Applications of cannabis sativa L. in food and its therapeutic potential: From a prohibited drug to a nutritional supplement. *Molecules*, 26(24), 7699. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26247699>

During the sensory evaluation, the cookies with 20% uncooked hemp flour and approximately 15% roasted hemp flour were assessed to be more acceptable by the panelists in terms of overall acceptability. Cannabis' nutritional characteristics in cookie studies demonstrated that it might be used as an alternative food component in the production of functional and nutritious products."³⁹

If we therefore take this generalized data for Marijuana Cookie production, adhere to the 20% maximum concentration data of the study cited, and apply it to the case of St. George where he was found to possess 460 g of Marijuana Cookies, its reality, there would have only been 92g of Marijuana therein. Which means, he would have only been indicted for a charge of possession under par. 3 of Section 11, Article 2, RA 9165, instead of par. 2 thereof which carried a much higher penalty. In fact, under the afore-discussed Plea-Bargaining Matrix, he would have qualified to plea bargain to Sec. 12 of Art. 2 and availed of probation.

The impact is quite glaring. This alone justifies the government to be more quantitative in its view on Purity as it does spell quite a difference to the outcome of any drug case.

LIMITATIONS IN TESTING.

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crimes (UNODC), through its Laboratory and Scientific Service, in Vienna, Austria published a manual for use by national drug analysis laboratories titled the "Recommended Methods for the Identification and Analysis

³⁹ See note 38. TABLE 2

of Cannabis and Cannabis Products”^{40 41} which set forth the very basis for the standard operating protocols adopted by the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency and Philippine National Police Chemistry Laboratories.

The manual prescribes the method for the determination of the existence of various prohibited drugs, including Cannabis and Cannabis Products⁴², the latter of which encompasses what is referred to in the Philippines and many other jurisdictions as Marijuana.

According to the US Department of Health and Human Services “the word “*marijuana*” refers to parts of or products from the plant *Cannabis sativa* that contain substantial amounts of tetrahydrocannabinol (THC). THC is the substance that’s primarily responsible for the effects of marijuana on a person’s mental state. Some cannabis plants contain very little THC.”⁴³

Nonetheless, the distinction is not relevant to this point – whatever name is used, it is the THC – the very organic compound

⁴⁰ United Nations. (2022). *Recommended methods for the identification and analysis* ... United Nations Office on Drugs and Crimes. https://www.unodc.org/documents/scientific/Recommended_methods_for_the_Identification_and_Analysis_of_Cannabis_and_Cannabis_products.pdf

⁴¹ Hereinafter referred to as “Manual” for brevity.

⁴² See Note 40. Page 2. Section 1.2 “Purpose and Use of Manual”.

⁴³ U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. (n.d.). *Cannabis (marijuana) and cannabinoids: What you need to know*. National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health. [https://www.nccih.nih.gov/health/cannabis-marijuana-and-cannabinoids-what-you-need-to-know#:~:text=The%20word%20%22cannabis%22refers%20to,amounts%20of%20tetrahydrocannabinol%20\(THC\).](https://www.nccih.nih.gov/health/cannabis-marijuana-and-cannabinoids-what-you-need-to-know#:~:text=The%20word%20%22cannabis%22refers%20to,amounts%20of%20tetrahydrocannabinol%20(THC).)

that is causative of the altered mental state for which Cannabis and Marijuana are taken recreationally, that is the one tested by forensic chemists of the PDEA or the PNP.

Types of Testing Under Prevailing Rules

The Manual prescribes two general means of identifying whether a test sample contains Cannabis or Cannabis Products:

1. Physical Test
2. Chemical Test

The Physical Test, in brief, employs the use of comparative observation in the determination of the presence of Cannabis – that is, the observable traits are compared to generally known forms of Cannabis and Cannabis products. For example, the presence of twigs, buds and leaf fragments is indicative of dried cannabis used primarily by smoking the same in rolls.

However, such observations find no relevance in the prosecution of possession or sale charges of Cannabis or Cannabis products because doubt can be raised as to their identity since many other plant products may have similar observable traits. Take for example rolled tobacco and papaya leaves which could present as leaf fragments, twigs, and buds as well.

In the Philippines, the Chemical Test employed is the Duquenois-Levin Test, which is a three-part test, through its

reagent's reaction with THC in marijuana to produce a purple bi-layer as a positive result. The reactive ingredients in this test kit are vanillin, ethanol, and acetaldehyde which, in an acidic environment would react with a vacant para-carbon relative to the hydroxyl group in the Phenol group of THC.⁴⁴ The reaction, as mentioned produces a positive reaction by way of a purple coloration thus signaling presence of the THC by mere inference as what is chemically signified is the presence of a Phenol Group with a free para-carbon.

As a side note, the above discussion does showcase a leading complaint against the use of the Duquenois-Levin Test as again it does not necessarily give a positive result for the presence of THC, but the Phenol Group in THC has a free para-carbon. Consequently, any substance containing a similar phenol group that would theoretically interact with the test kit, potentially resulting in a false positive outcome.

Kelly et al. (2012) found that among forty-two samples examined, patchouli, spearmint, and eucalyptus showed positive results for marijuana when tested using the Duquenois-Levin Test. These findings indicate that the test lacks specificity and may produce false positives. Consequently, it cannot be deemed reliable for prosecuting or convicting individuals for violations of anti-marijuana laws since it fails to establish conclusive evidence of marijuana presence beyond a reasonable doubt. Despite claims by law enforcement personnel and the test kit manufacturer asserting the Duquenois-Levin Test's specificity and high accuracy, it is evident that

⁴⁴ Jacobs, A. D., & Steiner, R. R. (2014). Detection of the duquenois-levine chromophore in a marijuana sample. *Forensic Science International*, 239, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2014.02.031>

in court, police officers often inaccurately testify to marijuana identification solely based on the Duquenois-Levin test and other non-specific screening tests, resulting in unjust convictions. This situation leads to the infringement of constitutionally guaranteed rights to a fair trial and due process, causing numerous wrongful convictions related to marijuana offenses. Although this study does take into consideration the forensic viability of the Duquenois-Levin Test in the context of American Legal System.

Nonetheless, granting without necessarily concluding that the Duquenois-Levin Test does provide for a viable result in the identification of the presence of THC in a sample, ergo, marijuana, it does so only qualitatively as it is a test that only yields positive or negative.

It is qualitative as opposed to a quantitative measurement of the amount of THC/ Marijuana in each sample. As stated beforehand, PCPL Melvin Manual estimated that the detection limit of the Duquenois-Levin Test is about 20 ppb or 0.000002 %. According to O'Neal et al. (2000), detection limits of these spot tests for drugs, which include the Duquenois-Levin Test, is at 0.00001 g to 0.0005 g (1 microgram to 50 micrograms).⁴⁵ This is very sensitive testing – which is in and of itself great if the objective is to simply detect the mere presence of the prohibited drug. But this essentially tells us nothing, if we need to ascertain the amount of the drugs in the sample.

⁴⁵ O'Neal, C. L., Crouch, D. J., & Fatah, A. A. (2000). Validation of twelve chemical spot tests for the detection of drugs of abuse. *Forensic Science International*, 109(3), 189–201. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0379-0738\(99\)00235-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0379-0738(99)00235-2)

The only quantitative conclusion that can be reasonably drawn from the Duquenois-Levin Test is that at the very least, the sample does in fact contain 0.00001 grams – but if such would be the basis alone to indict a person, more so, convict someone for substances weighing 460 g, surely, basic constitutional protections are violated.

DETERMINATION OF ACTUAL AMOUNTS OF THC/MARIJUANA IN A SAMPLE IS NOT IMPOSSIBLE

Several laboratory techniques are prescribed by the Manual⁴⁶ that not only give us a qualitative determination of the presence of the THC/ Marijuana in each sample but also allow quantitative data gathering.

The Manual proposes the following:

1. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) is a widely employed method for separating and detecting drugs. It is cost-effective, swift, and offers flexibility in selecting both the stationary and mobile phases, accommodating a diverse range of substances from highly polar to non-polar materials. When paired with a drug reference standard, TLC aids in identifying components and is often combined with other techniques to confirm the drug's identity conclusively⁴⁷.
2. Liquid chromatography (LC) stands as a widely employed and sturdy analytical method utilized not only for segregating

⁴⁶ See Note 40

⁴⁷ See Note40. Page 41

components within mixtures but also for quantitative purposes. Given the herbal composition of cannabis plant materials, it is often imperative to undertake sample purification before analysis. It is important to avoid the use of basic conditions when quantifying acidic cannabinoids, as this can impact the retention time of the analyte, peak shape, and selectivity. Ensuring well-resolved peaks corresponding to cannabinoids is crucial, as any co-elution with the target analyte can compromise the accuracy of quantitation results.

An advantage of employing LC for cannabinoid quantitation lies in its capability to easily quantify both neutral and acidic cannabinoids without necessitating decarboxylation. Consequently, the total THC content of the sample can be determined by summing the quantities of THC and THA from the two peaks observed in the chromatogram.⁴⁸

3. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) is a highly effective method that merges the separation abilities of traditional LC or ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) with the detection capabilities of a tandem mass spectrometer. This combination leads to a substantial enhancement in selectivity and a decrease in interference between active ingredients and the matrix. LC-MS/MS exhibits exceptional sensitivity and selectivity, making it well-suited for both qualitative and quantitative analysis of cannabinoids at low concentrations

⁴⁸ See Note 40. Page 54

within intricate herbal mixtures and matrices, such as those found in cannabis edibles.⁴⁹

V – CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The confluence of legal and factual data points to the following conclusion: The “regardless of degree of purity” provision is INVALID as it violates the juridical condition of commensurability of penalty which is a principle upheld in our jurisdiction on various levels as it is supported by international principles on human rights and the science of forensic testing of dangerous drugs.

The Human Rights implications of a lack of a more incisive Drug Policy were well discussed in a paper by Lines et al, when in concluding their article, they posited that “Article 28 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states: “Everyone is entitled to a social and international order in which the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration can be fully realized.” However, the rights enshrined within the Declaration will never be realized in the context of drug control when the international legal order that defines the regime continues to perpetuate an environment of human rights risk, and when that regime is subject to little or no human rights scrutiny. International Guidelines on Human Rights and Drug Control would be a critical tool for closing this gap and would help operationalize a human rights-based approach to drug control. Such guidelines are necessary and long overdue, and their advent would be a fitting way

⁴⁹ See Note 40. Page 58

to celebrate the 70th anniversary of the Universal Declaration in 2018.”⁵⁰

The removal of this qualificatory provision is scientifically possible as advancements in testing technology have been shown to ascertain the degree of purity for mixtures of a variety of classes of prohibited and controlled drugs and their precursors as the science in chemical testing has come a long way, the perceived limitations of drug testing ten or twenty years ago no longer exist now. No less than the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crimes has prescribed multiple testing systems that allow for a quantitative analysis of the drug in question.

According to Hadener et al. (2019), there is a new HPLC-DAD method that meets the increasing global demand for fast, cost-effective, and reliable cannabis potency testing. HPLC offers advantages over previously reported GC-based methods as neutral and acidic cannabinoids can be quantified separately, thus allowing direct determination of the original cannabinoid profile as well as more accurate quantification of total cannabinoid contents.⁵¹

Indeed, Chemistry Laboratories play a vital role in Drug Control efforts as they provide for the forensic backbone of prosecution of

⁵⁰ Lines R, Elliott R, Hannah J, Schleifer R, Avafia T, Barrett D. The Case for International Guidelines on Human Rights and Drug Control. *Health Hum Rights*. 2017 Jun;19(1):231-236. PMID: 28630555; PMCID: PMC5473052.

⁵¹ Hädener, M., König, S., & Weinmann, W. (2019). Quantitative determination of CBD and THC and their acid precursors in confiscated cannabis samples by HPLC-dad. *Forensic Science International*, 299, 142–150.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2019.03.046>

drug offenses. In paper by Diokno (2016)⁵², she found that the UNODC emphasizes the significant role of forensic science in the criminal justice system. It asserts that forensic services play a crucial role in ensuring an efficient and fair legal process by offering unbiased and timely information across various stages of criminal proceedings. For instance, police rely on forensic services to identify suspects during investigations, while attorneys and judges utilize them during trials. The primary aim of forensic science is to aid in uncovering the truth by supplying the criminal justice system with objective evidence and by posing inquiries aimed at establishing the guilt or innocence of an accused individual.

Therefore, it is recommended that forensic services be administered by highly skilled and impartial entities. Moreover, guidance and counsel from PDEA and PNP laboratories would greatly enhance the investigation and prosecution of drug-related cases, particularly concerning the proper collection, handling, and packaging of drug evidence seized, recovered, or surrendered.

It is the recommendation that the law be amended to remove the “regardless of degree of purity” provision or at the very least, to clarify and further qualify the provision to only relate to mixtures at a threshold of purity that would justify the inclusion of the added chemicals in the weighing, say if the sample is found to be 85% or 90% that of the dangerous drug, then the entire sample shall be weighed as a whole, or say that if the dangerous drug mixture is 50% or less the dangerous drug then the sample’s percentage shall be

⁵² Diokno, M. S. I. (2016). Forensic Science in the Prosecution of Illegal Drugs Case. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 147(1), 1-8.

considered in the determination of the true mass of the dangerous drugs in the sample.

Furthermore, this qualification on purity can be a subject of judicial interpretation as the terms "regardless" and "purity" may be defined by the court – as the interpretations of law is a primary function of the Court. Hence, the Court can so very well interpret that the provision "regardless of purity" would only be with respect to how in the organic synthesis of all substances there is a scientific impossibility of manufacturing a yield that is 100% of only the sought product and that impurities such as unreacted precursors, catalysts, by-products, and even differentiation in isomeric products, is what is meant when the law disregards the substance's purity. The Court may very well interpret those mixtures of dangerous drugs with inert substances such as flour, fruit juice, or teas, and even as mundane as water, is not what the law envisions.

Whatever approach may be undertaken, one thing is certain – the need to investigate the very real implications of this provision of law, is pressing. Change not only needs to come by way of executive action, in the fight against dangerous drugs, and the balancing act to protect human rights - legislation or judicial intervention is necessary, as well.

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